

Free Electron Molecular Orbital Treatment of the Absorption Spectra of Chain Substituted Polymethine Dyes

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The absorption spectra of some dyes containing nitrogen and other substituents in the chromophoric chain have been calculated by using the free electron wave functions and a simple perturbation technique. Correspondence with experiment is satisfactory and was found to be better than that obtained by employing Kuhn's procedure.

KUHN¹ has extended the Free Electron Molecular Orbital (FEMO) method to linear dye molecules in which the central methine group is replaced by nitrogen. It was proposed by him that the simple potential box model for a symmetrical polymethine dye suffers a disturbance on introduction of a nitrogen atom in place of the methine group and the potential energy in the region of the newly added nitrogen atom is less than the rest of the chain. Assuming a narrow and deep potential drop at the position of the nitrogen atom ($-U$) and using Kronig and Penney's model, the Schrodinger equation was solved by taking appropriate boundary and normalization conditions and expressions for the frequency shift due to nitrogen replacement could be obtained. Although, the inherent principle of the Kuhn's method is quite simple, the derivations of the eigen-functions and eigen-values involve rather lengthy and tedious numerical solutions of a number of trigonometric equations.

Recently, McGlynn, Vanquickenborne, Kinoshita and Carroll² have suggested a simple perturbation treatment based on the potential well model, similar to one proposed by Kuhn. They have applied it to a very limited number of dyes and have obtained quite encouraging results. In the present paper, we report extension of the method to a number of different series of azadyes. We also propose to discuss the applicability of the concept to some chain substituted dyes whose absorption maxima undergo changes with respect to the unsubstituted dyes, a phenomenon similar to aza replacement.

The perturbation technique may briefly be described as following :

Let us consider a dye involving eight π -electrons, so that the first intense absorption may be associated with the transition $E_4 \rightarrow E_8$. The introduction of the nitrogen atom is equivalent to introducing a perturbing potential $U_p = -U$ for $(L/2) - b \leq x \leq (L/2) + b$ where $2b$ is the width of the subwell and L is the effective length of the box.

The energy correction (ΔE_4) for the highest occupied molecular orbital (ϕ_4), according to the first order perturbation theory is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_4 &= \int_0^L \phi_4 \hat{U}_p \phi_4 dx = \int_{[(L/2)-b]}^{[(L/2)+b]} -\phi_4 \hat{U} \phi_4 dx \\ &= -\frac{2U}{L} \int_{[(L/2)-b]}^{[(L/2)+b]} \sin^2 \frac{4\pi x}{L} dx \\ &= -\frac{4Ub}{L} \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sin(8\pi b/L)}{(8\pi b/L)} \right] \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the lowest unoccupied MO shifts by an amount

$$\Delta E_5 = \int_0^L \phi_5 \hat{U}_p \phi_5 dx = -\frac{4Ub}{L} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sin(10\pi b/L)}{(10\pi b/L)} \right] \quad (2)$$

Setting C-N distance equal to C-C distance, i. e., $b=L/16$, it is possible to eliminate any explicit occurrence of L and thus the net frequency shift $\Delta E_5 - \Delta E_4$ can be found out in terms of $U \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Method of Calculation :

1. In all cases the free electron path is assumed to terminate at one bond length beyond the end atoms³. Thus if a molecule involves 8 bonds in the chromophoric chain, the effective length L is given

by $(8+2)$ C-C bonds and hence $b = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{L}{10} = \frac{L}{20}$.

2. For sulphur-containing dyes, on account of the ability of sulphur to act as a resonance transmitter, the number of π -electrons in the chromophoric chain is calculated by considering sulphur in the chromophoric chain. For example, in case of

a monomethine benzothiazole dye the number of π -electrons shall be given by⁴,

$$5(\text{for } 5\text{C atoms}) + 3(2\text{N atoms}) + 2(\text{sulphur}) = 10$$

3. For quinoline-2 dyes, the chromophoric chain is taken as the one involving a part of the benzene ring at one end, i. e.,

Taking into account the above postulates and following the method used for the derivations of Eqs. (1) and (2), the following set of formulae are obtained for the frequency shift for symmetrical dyes. λ_x is the absorption maxima for the dye in which the central $-\text{CH}=\text{}$ group has either been replaced by $-\text{N}=\text{}$ or has undergone a substitution to $-\text{CR}=\text{}$.

For the symmetrical monomethine and pentamethine dyes the perturbing potential U has been calculated from the monomethine dyes using the experimental frequency shift and the appropriate formula in Table 1. Using the value of U the

Sl. No.	Nature of the dye	No. of π -electrons	b	Frequency shift (cm^{-1}) $\frac{1}{\lambda_X} - \frac{1}{\lambda_{\text{CH}}}$
1.	Benzoxazole (Pentamethine)	10	L/20	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_5 = 0.1140 U$
2a.	Benzothiazole (Monomethine)	10	L/12	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_5 = 0.0318 U$
2b.	Benzothiazole (Pentamethine)	14	L/20	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_7 = 0.0608 U$
3a.	Quinoline-2 (Monomethine)	10	L/20	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_5 = 0.1140 U$
3b.	Quinoline-2 (Pentamethine)	14	L/28	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_7 = 0.0843 U$
4.	Quinoline-4 (Pentamethine)	14	L/28	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_7 = 0.0843 U$
5.	Oxonols (Trimethine)	10	L/20	$\Delta E_6 - \Delta E_5 = 0.1140 U$

frequency shift for the pentamethine analogue have been calculated and the results compared with experiment. For all other dyes, where only one series was available, U has been calculated by using the observed frequency shift for one member of the series and using this value of U the frequency shifts for other members of the series are predicted. The results are summarised in the following tables.

It can be seen from the Tables 2, 3 and 4 that in view of the simplicity of the model the correspondence between the calculated and observed values is quite satisfactory. Regarding the two

Sl. No.	Nature of end group	$U \times 10^{-5} \text{cm}^{-1}$ calculated from the monomethine dyes.	$\lambda_{\text{CH}} \text{nm}$	$\frac{1}{\lambda_N} - \frac{1}{\lambda_{\text{CH}}}$ (Pentamethine) Calcd.	λ_{Nnm} Obsd.
a.	Benzothiazole	0.4623	665	0.0281×10^6	560 555
b.	4-Phenylthiazole	0.5754	660	0.0350×10^6	536 555
c.	α -Naphthothiazole	0.5220	690	0.0320×10^6	565 575
d.	β -Naphthothiazole	0.5220	690	0.0320×10^6	565 570
e.	Quinoline-2	0.3910	710	0.1738×10^6	575 565

methods available, Kuhn's and the present method, their relative correspondence with experiment may be seen from Table 5 for the symmetrical cyanines and their γ -aza analogues.

TABLE 3—CHAIN SUBSTITUTED CYANINES (PENTAMETHINE)

The perturbing potential U is calculated from the benzoxazole dye:

$$\lambda_{\text{CH}} = 580 \text{ nm}, \lambda_{\text{CR}_1} = 562 \text{ nm}, \lambda_{\text{CR}_2} = 562 \text{ nm}$$

$$U(R_1) = 0.0482 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-1}; U(R_2) = 0.0482 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

Sl. No.	Nature of B	λ_{CH} nm	λ_{CR_1} nm Calcd.	Obsd.	λ_{CR_2} nm Calcd.	Obsd.
a.	Benzothiazole	665	652	616	652	634
b.	Quinoline-2	710	690	665	690	675
c.	Quinoline-4	810	784	762	784	778

TABLE 4—CHAIN SUBSTITUTED OXONOLS (TRIMETHINE)

U has been calculated from the *N*-methyl rhodanine dye:
 $\lambda_{\text{CH}} = 620 \text{ nm}; \lambda_{\text{CR}_1} = 481 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{CR}_2} = 488 \text{ nm}$

$$U(R_1) = 0.412 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-1}; U(R_2) = 0.382 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

Sl. No.	Nature of A	λ_{CH}	λ_{CR_1} nm Calcd.	Obsd.	λ_{CR_2} nm Calcd.	Obsd.
a.	3-Phenyl thiohydantoin	610	474	470	482	484
b.	Indane, 1,3-dione	555	440	434	447	443
c.	1-Phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone	535	428	422	432	420
d.	3-Phenyl-isooxazolone	535	428	419	432	—

TABLE 5

Nature of the end group	λ_{Nnm}^s	λ_{Nnm}	λ_{Nnm}
	Kuhn	Perturbation	abs.
Benzothiazole	628	560	555
4-Phenyl thiazole	609.8	536	555
α -Naphthothiazole	640.2	565	575
β -Naphthothiazole	640.2	565	570
Quinoline-2	581.1	575	565

Thus it is seen that with regard to the prediction of spectra, the present method gives remarkably better result than the one suggested by Kuhn.

The spectra have been recorded with a Hilger-Watts UV visible spectrophotometer.

Experimental

The method of preparation of the benzoxazolyl and benzothiazolyl dyes (listed in Tables 3 and 4) has already been reported⁶.

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